

Engines under control

The challenge of putting an end to
fishing vessel engine power fraud
in the Spanish Mediterranean

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Table of Contents

1. Executive summary	3	6. Installation and certification process: How does fraud occur?	14
2. Origin of the collapse of fishing in the Mediterranean	4	Steps to be taken and organisations involved	14
Increased engine power and overfishing	4	How does engine power fraud occur?	15
Impact of the Multiannual Plan for Demersal Stocks in the Western Mediterranean Sea	7	7. Challenges and solutions for engine regularisation: The horsepower trading market and fishing capacity limits	16
3. Engine power as a key indicator for measuring fishing capacity	7	8. Conclusions	18
Fishing capacity, underestimated as a result of engine power fraud	8	Recommendations	18
4. Regulatory framework	9	References and notes	19
5. Engine power fraud: Comparison between official and unofficial data	11		
Methodology	11		
Results	11		

Credits

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1. Executive summary

The fishing fleet in the Spanish Mediterranean has been facing a critical situation for decades that threatens its viability, both from an economic standpoint and in terms of the sustainability of marine resources. Despite an enormous effort by the fishing industry and improvements in the state of fisheries, especially since the introduction of the Multiannual Plan for Demersal Stocks in the Western Mediterranean Sea in 2019, low levels of sustainability and profitability remain alarming.

Among the factors that worsen this crisis are various irregularities, ranging from the manipulation of the selectivity of fishing gear to the sale of undeclared products. However, the most significant and common irregularity is fraud related to the power of engines installed on fishing vessels. This type of fraud not only compromises the sustainability of species but also causes serious distortions within the industry, leading to inequalities and allowing unfair competition for those who operate using engines that are significantly more powerful than are permitted by law.

This study focuses on fraud detected in the trawl and purse seine fleets, two fishing methods that require high engine power to deploy and retrieve fishing gear. Based on the analysis of 50 vessels in the Spanish Mediterranean, many irregularities have been detected, such as the manipulation of engine technical data sheets, the alteration of engine power limiters, and non-compliance with legal limits on the maximum power allowed (904 horsepower for trawlers and 455 horsepower for purse seiners since 2022).

The evidence is overwhelming: 94% of the vessels analysed appear to have fraudulent engines, with actual power far exceeding the certified power, and 20% of the vessels directly exceed the established legal power limits. In many cases, the difference is not marginal, but rather double, triple, or even up to eight times the power declared in the Fishing Fleet Register. **This situation completely distorts the calculation of fishing effort, the main management tool in the Mediterranean for these vessels,** and reduces the effectiveness of management and conservation measures, as the official figures seriously underestimate the real impact of fishing activity on the ecosystem.

The study is based on information obtained through interviews with fishers, port staff, and experts from the fishing industry, as well as from technical and scientific studies, and official documents obtained through requests for access to information. The findings reveal a systematic, persistent problem that is not limited to fishers but also involves other stakeholders, including the fisheries administration, engine manufacturers and installers, and certification bodies.

Oceana has been reporting these irregularities to the maritime and fisheries authorities for years.¹ However, to date, the administrations have not taken effective measures to correct the situation. Despite the widespread impact on marine ecosystems and public resources, engine power fraud is still a taboo topic that many prefer not

to broach, either because of its complexity or the difficulty of finding viable solutions.

In this regard, we advocate strengthening fisheries control systems, adopting an engine regularisation programme, and implementing effective deterrent measures to prevent fraud in the long term.

These measures are a key step towards ensuring fairer and more sustainable fishing in the Spanish Mediterranean. With this report, we aim to contribute to a constructive dialogue between administrations, fishers' guilds, and other key stakeholders, in order to find viable solutions for the industry and for the future of the sea.

2. Origin of the collapse of fishing in the Mediterranean

Increased engine power and overfishing

Fishing in the Mediterranean Sea as a whole is in a critical state. Sixty-five percent of the stocks assessed in this region are subject to overfishing, with some being exploited at levels between two to five times higher than the maximum sustainable yield.² This is the result of decades of mismanagement and a lack of effective planning to ensure the sustainability of the fishing sector and marine resources.

For decades, national and regional administrations have failed to take the necessary measures to prevent the construction and operation of more vessels than marine resources could sustain.³ Overcapacity has been particularly severe in the Mediterranean, which is considered by the FAO to be the most overexploited sea in the world.² Nor have measures been taken to prevent the destruction of essential habitats for species (such as breeding, nursery, feeding, and migration areas) and fisheries management has failed to adapt to technological advances that have increasingly allowed fisheries exploit more remote areas, and to do so more easily and precisely.

Although ecological deterioration and species declines were already evident in the 1980s, technological innovations managed to temporarily maintain catch levels, masking the scale of the problem.⁴ However, the ecosystem has reached its limit and fisheries have shown a clear downward trend for roughly two decades. Neither the modernisation of the fleet nor the expansion of markets have managed to curb the loss of economic viability in the industry, which has suffered a steady decline.

Evolution of the number of vessels, registered fishing power, and catch volumes for the period 2006-2023

Figure 1: Historical record of the maritime fishing fleet across all years, in the autonomous communities of the Balearic Islands, Region of Murcia, Catalonia, the Valencian Community, and Andalusia, for all fishing methods.

Source: Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca. (2024). *Anuario de Pesca Marítima*. <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadistica-digital/powerbi-pesca>

Between 2006 and 2023, the fleet in the autonomous communities with fishing activity in the Mediterranean (the Balearic Islands, Murcia, Catalonia, the Valencian Community, and Andalusia) experienced a significant reduction in size, going from 4861 vessels with a total engine power of 327 000 kW (445 000 hp) to 3024 vessels with a total engine power of 264 000 kW (359 000 hp).

Although both variables decreased, the reduction was not proportional: while the number of vessels fell by 38%, total engine power only decreased by 19%. This difference suggests that, despite the demolition of vessels, the aggregate propulsion capacity of the active fleet remained high.

One noteworthy change was the increase in engine power registered between 2020 and 2021, from 201 866 kW to 265 792 kW. This increase of more than 30% in engine power from one year to the next could be related to engine regularisation processes.

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Catch volumes have also fallen sharply, from 130 000 tonnes in 2006 to 53 000 tonnes in 2023. In recent years, a significant reduction has occurred, which was necessary to curb overfishing. This reduction was largely due to the entry into force of the Multiannual Plan for Demersal Stocks in the Western Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 2: Temporal trend in catches by the Spanish fishing fleet in the Mediterranean Sea

Source: Eurostat. (2025). https://doi.org/10.2908/FISH_CA_ATL37

Until the 2000s, most shipowners chose to modernise their vessels by installing more powerful engines to increase their fishing capacity, maintain catch levels, and add economic value to their vessels. This modernisation was made possible, to a large extent, by public aid and subsidies which facilitated the acquisition and installation of more powerful engines. Added to this was competition among vessels; reaching fishing grounds first meant gaining access to the most valuable resources, contributing to a veritable race for power and further intensifying the pressure on fisheries resources.

In 2013, in response to an ecological and economic crisis in fisheries, the European Union's Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) set as its main objective the restoration and maintenance of fish stocks above levels capable of producing maximum sustainable yield. To achieve this, it committed to setting fishing mortality levels consistent with this objective by 2020, with the aim of ensuring the long-term sustainability of commercial species and fishing activity itself. The CFP forced a significant restructuring of the industry, with adjustments to fishing capacity in an attempt to balance it with the available resources. Although there is still some way to go, the achievements of the CFP are

undeniable, with an increasingly sustainable and profitable fishing industry. However, such progress has come at a great cost, forcing many operators to reduce their activity or, in some cases, to abandon fishing altogether.

Impact of the Multiannual Plan for Demersal Stocks in the Western Mediterranean Sea

The entry into force of the Multiannual Plan for Demersal Stocks in the Western Mediterranean Sea in 2019 has had a profound impact on bottom trawlers targeting demersal species such as hake, red shrimp, deep-water rose shrimp, and Norway lobster. Although the overall objective of the CFP was to achieve sustainable exploitation levels by 2020, in the case of the Western Mediterranean, the deadline was extended to December 2025. Despite this extension, the target is still far from being met. As a result, in December 2024, the Council of the European Union was obliged to approve a drastic reduction in fishing effort (measured in fishing days) for 2025. In the case of the Spanish bottom trawling fleet, the initial allocation was limited to an average of only 27 working days per year. However, as a result of the compensation mechanism approved,

vessels can maintain virtually the same number of fishing days as in the previous year if they adopt sustainability measures such as improving gear selectivity, reducing impacts on the seabed, or adopting new fishing closures. This situation has provoked a strong reaction from the industry, which has expressed its dissatisfaction through demonstrations and strikes.

Without denying the huge efforts made by the industry over the last five years, unfortunately, overfishing continues and resources are still far from sustainable levels.⁵ Future fisheries management in the Mediterranean must focus on striking a real balance between the economic viability of the industry and the conservation of marine ecosystems.

3. Engine power as a key indicator for measuring fishing capacity

Fishing restrictions are not limited to setting Total Allowable Catches (TACs; i.e. the maximum tonnage of a given species that can be fished), but also include the control of fishing effort through regulations on a fleet and its activity, such as the number of fishing days authorised. In the Mediterranean Sea, where fishing is mostly multi-species (i.e. various species are caught in the same operation), TACs are seldom applied. The main management system in this region for fisheries with multi-species gears, such as bottom trawls, is the control of fishing effort.

Since the adoption of the 2006 Mediterranean Regulation, and more recently, the Multi-Annual Plan for Demersal Stocks in the Western Mediterranean Sea in 2019, measures to adjust

fishing effort to available fishing opportunities have focused on:

- Reducing the total number of vessels operating in the region;
- Limiting the time available for fishing (days or hours) for each vessel;
- Establishing catch limits (TACs) for certain commercial species;
- Encouraging the use of more selective and less harmful fishing gears, such as by increasing the mesh size of nets;
- Restricting fishing activities in essential fish habitats.

These initiatives to limit fishing effort are, however, directly linked to vessels' fishing capacity. Indeed, the number of fishing days allowed multiplies their impact depending on the size, engine power, and characteristics of each vessel.

The fishing capacity of a vessel is influenced by various factors, of which the following are the most widely accepted in the scientific and technical literature and by fisheries managers:

The size of the vessel, measured in gross tonnage (GT);

The power of the engine installed on the vessel, measured in kilowatts (kW) or horsepower (hp);

The types, models, and sizes of the fishing gear used, such as nets, longlines, purse seines, or trawls, among others.

Of the above variables, engine power is a key indicator of a vessel's fishing capacity, as it directly influences its efficiency, range, and catching potential. Studies such as those by the [European Commission](#)⁶ and [Eigaard et al.](#),⁷ confirm that the relationship between engine power and catching capacity is clear, particularly in bottom trawl fishing. **Engine power translates directly into thrust capacity, resulting in higher maximum navigation speeds and allowing the use of larger and heavier gear.** Faster navigation speeds allow vessels to travel more quickly between fishing grounds and ports, while faster speeds while fishing and the deployment of larger gear allow vessels to fish across a greater volume of water or a broader area of the seabed.

Despite this, and the measures that have been adopted to reduce fishing effort, a key obstacle to achieving truly sustainable exploitation of marine resources continues to be ignored: fraud in vessel engine power.

Fishing capacity, underestimated as a result of engine power fraud

Irregularities in engine power, where the actual power of the engine installed is much higher than that certified in the fishing fleet register, seriously distort the system of fishing effort management, as the actual fishing capacity of a vessel also depends on the power of its engine. How is it possible that, in a context of historical overexploitation in which fishing must be drastically reduced, that action is being taken to reduce fishing effort but not to reduce the actual fishing capacity of the fleet? How can it be that no action is being taken against the use of illegal engines, and that it is even permitted to increase the maximum permitted power? Simply put, it is because this fraud is so widespread that the solution is complex. None of the actors involved wishes to take on this responsibility and, in the end, the fisheries resources and the industry itself pay the price.

This study does not attempt to reformulate the calculation of fishing effort or capacity, nor to analyse whether the calculation method used is the most appropriate from an equitable point of view. It does, however, emphasise that engine power is an essential parameter in any naval engineering project and must be taken into account in any fisheries management strategy.

It is true that engine power can be a more or less relevant variable depending on the fleet segment, the area of operation, and the type of fishery.

For example, in goose barnacle fisheries, harvesting is carried out manually on the rocks, and the vessel's engine is used mainly for safety purposes (i.e. to keep the vessel close to the coast and allow for a rapid response to adverse conditions). Another example is that of octopus pot fisheries, where fishing capacity does not depend on engine power, but on the number of pots that can be legally deployed.

However, in most types of fishing, and particularly trawling, it is undeniable that engine power directly influences the speed, time, and use of fishing gear, as well as the size and weight of the gear that can be used. Therefore, it is a key factor for calculating fishing effort and capacity. Underestimating effort and capacity will always result in underestimating the real impact of the fleet, which inevitably leads to overfishing.

4. Regulatory framework

The control of engine power is regulated by a set of European and national regulations that establish certification and verification procedures to ensure that fishing capacity complies with authorised limits.

At the European level, Regulation 1224/2009 on fisheries control establishes that it *“shall be prohibited to fish with a fishing vessel that is equipped with an engine the power of which exceeds the one established in the fishing licence”* (Article 39.1).

This regulation has recently been amended by Regulation 2023/2842, which adds an incentive to regularise engines whose power exceeds the authorised limit: *“When a catching vessel exceeds the authorised engine power set out in the fishing licence, a regularisation may be carried out”* (Art. 39). Likewise, it introduces the obligation to install systems for continuous monitoring of engine power on certain vessels (Art. 39a.2). However, this obligation will not enter into force until January 2028, and the development of specific criteria on how these systems should work and on which vessels they should be installed is still pending.

Some of these rules are defined in more detail in Articles 61-63 of Implementing Regulation 404/2011, which establish certain procedures for certifying engine power, as well as the need to establish a verification plan for inspectors to physically inspect certain vessels and verify their actual power.

In the Spanish context, Royal Decree 502/2022 of 27 June, which regulates fishing in national fishing grounds, establishes specific engine power limits according to the type of vessel:

- » For vessels engaged in bottom trawling in the Mediterranean, Article 12.1 stipulates that the engine power may not exceed 665 kW, which is equivalent to 904 hp.
- » For vessels engaged in purse seine fishing in the Mediterranean, Article 18 sets a limit of 330 kW, equivalent to 445.5 hp.

This new limit of 904 hp for bottom trawlers represents a very significant increase with respect to the previous regulation. Between 1988 and 2022, the legal limit was 500 hp, close to half the current limit.⁸

The reason for this increase in the legal limit is unclear, as no public justification has ever been provided. According to some fishers interviewed for this study, the increase could be an attempt by the Spanish administration to regularise a widespread situation of non-compliance. For decades, many vessels have operated with engines that far exceeded the previous limit, with the apparent consent of the authorities. If the 500 hp threshold had been maintained, most of the fleet would have been rendered inoperable, as the engines would have had to be replaced to comply with this limit. With the increase in the maximum permitted limit to 904 hp, it has been easier for shipowners to regularise the actual power of their engines without having to change them or replace them with new ones.

On the other hand, Royal Decree 1044/2022 of 27 December on the regulation of the fishing fleet establishes the possibility of developing verification plans involving the various competent authorities, with the aim of ensuring that engine power does not exceed the limits set out in fishing licences. Article 5.3 underlines the European ban on fishing with a fishing vessel equipped with an engine whose power exceeds that established in the licence, and Article 15 details the procedures for regularising engine power.

Access to information on inspections, sanctions, and procedures for regularising engines

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Within the framework of this study, through requests for access to public information, we asked for the verification plans,⁹ as well as the inspection reports and irregularities detected by the public administration.

The information received reveals that a sampling plan was carried out, which selected a total of 1303 vessels classified as 'at risk' of not complying with official engine power limits. These 1303 vessels that operate nationally included the 589 bottom trawlers operating in the Mediterranean, but no purse seiners.

Of these 1303 vessels, a random sample of 101 vessels was selected to verify their characteristics and data in the official register. Through this process, vessels were identified that were suspected of having a higher engine power than was authorised.

Since 2019, only 14 physical inspections have been carried out. However, the administration has stated that it cannot provide the results of these verifications until final decisions have been made on the regularisation procedures resulting from such inspections.

With regard to the imposition of sanctions, the Spanish central administration has not been able

to provide data on the numbers of open cases or sanctions imposed, arguing that the competence to impose sanctions for engine power fraud lies with the autonomous communities. In this regard, the administration should be reminded that Article 93 of the new European Fisheries Control Regulation (2023/2842) requires EU Member States to publish a detailed annual report on the verifications and inspections performed, including the number of inspections, infringements detected, and sanctions imposed, regardless of whether or not the competence thereof is decentralised.

Finally, with regard to the regularisation of engines, since the entry into force of Royal Decree 1044/2022, only ten procedures have been completed. Of these, only two correspond to the Mediterranean, both concerning purse seine vessels engaged in fishing bluefin tuna. This number is particularly low in the context of widespread fraud in engine power. Furthermore, it has not been specified whether these regularisations have been imposed by the administration or whether they include voluntary requests from shipowners. This distinction is key for assessing the effectiveness of the regularisation process and the degree of compliance within the fishing industry.

Overall, these regulations reflect the evolution in the control of engine power, but they also raise questions about the effectiveness of the

policies implemented and the possible motivations underlying the regulatory changes.

5. Engine power fraud: Comparison between official and unofficial data

Methodology

An analysis of 50 vessels was based on fieldwork, on-site observations in various fishing ports, interviews with industry professionals, and a review of official data from the General Fishing Fleet Register. The aim was to compare the engine power declared in the official registers with the actual power installed and used on the vessels, in order to identify potential discrepancies and signs of irregularities.

To determine actual engine power values, individual interviews were conducted with shipowners and other professionals involved in operations in the ports. Some of the data obtained were cross-checked with documents which corroborated the statements made by the interviewees.

In order to protect the identity of shipowners and guarantee anonymity, the vessels mentioned in this study do not include any identifying information such as name or IMO number, thus avoiding any direct link to their identity.

Results

As mentioned in the previous section, current regulations establish a legal limit of 904 hp for trawlers (previously set at 500 hp, until 2022) and 450 hp for purse seiners. According to the official register, none of the 50 vessels analysed would exceed the legal limits currently in force. Under the regulations prior to 2022, only two trawlers would have exceeded the 500 hp legal limit at the time.

However, the analysis of unofficial data compiled for this report provides a radically different picture. The analysis reveals that 47 of the 50 vessels (94% of the total) operate with an engine power that is significantly higher than that certified. When compared with current legal limits, the data show that ten vessels (20% of the total) operate with a higher engine power than is permitted (see Table 1). Specifically, eight trawlers are operating with an engine power of between 980 and 1600 hp, and two seiners with an engine power of 500 and 600 hp. With respect to the previous legal limit of 500 hp for trawlers, 28 vessels (or 56% of the sample) exceeded it by a wide margin.

On average, the actual engine power per vessel is 660 hp, almost triple the average certified power of 288 hp. In some cases, this difference is up to

eight times higher than the power declared in the official register.

In aggregate terms, the 50 vessels analysed officially have a total of 14 393 certified hp, while the actual power amounts to 32 980 hp, thus double the declared fishing capacity.

These differences reveal a widespread pattern of fraud in the declaration of engine power and raise concerns about the effectiveness of control systems.

The magnitude of the problem is such that, on the one hand, a thorough review of the current verification mechanisms is needed and, on the other hand, a mass regularisation of certified engine power must be carried out.

Table 1. Comparison of certified engine power and estimated actual engine power in the vessels analysed, listed according to percentage difference.

Vessel	Fishing gear	Certified power (hp)	Actual power (hp)	Percentage difference
Vessel 1	Trawler	90	800	789%
Vessel 2	Trawler	31	250	706%
Vessel 3	Trawler	90	600	567%
Vessel 4	Trawler	50.3	300	496%
Vessel 5	Trawler	130	700	438%
Vessel 6	Trawler	82	400	388%
Vessel 7	Trawler	65	300	362%
Vessel 8	Trawler	153.7	650	323%
Vessel 9	Trawler	95	400	321%
Vessel 10	Trawler	72	300	317%
Vessel 11	Trawler	170	700	312%
Vessel 12	Trawler	127.8	500	291%
Vessel 13	Trawler	78	300	285%
Vessel 14	Trawler	106	400	277%
Vessel 15	Trawler	122	450	269%
Vessel 16	Trawler	219.7	800	264%
Vessel 17	Trawler	57	200	251%
Vessel 18	Trawler	242	800	231%
Vessel 19	Trawler	216	700	224%
Vessel 20	Trawler	500	1600	220%
Vessel 21	Trawler	190	600	218%
Vessel 22	Trawler	467	1400	199%
Vessel 23	Trawler	495	1400	182%
Vessel 24	Seiner	231.1	600	159%
Vessel 25	Trawler	352	900	155%

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Vessel	Fishing gear	Certified power (hp)	Actual power (hp)	Percentage difference
Vessel 26	Trawler	314	800	154%
Vessel 27	Trawler	470.6	1100	133%
Vessel 28	Trawler	435	1000	129%
Vessel 29	Trawler	200	450	125%
Vessel 30	Trawler	495	1100	122%
Vessel 31	Trawler	180	400	122%
Vessel 32	Seiner	180	400	122%
Vessel 33	Trawler	316	700	121%
Vessel 34	Seiner	187	400	113%
Vessel 35	Trawler	499	980	96%
Vessel 36	Trawler	740	1400	89%
Vessel 37	Trawler	428	800	86%
Vessel 38	Seiner	240	400	66%
Vessel 39	Trawler	430	700	62%
Vessel 40	Trawler	435	700	60%
Vessel 41	Trawler	500	800	60%
Vessel 42	Trawler	480	700	45%
Vessel 43	Trawler	566	800	41%
Vessel 44	Trawler	365	500	37%
Vessel 45	Trawler	375	500	33%
Vessel 46	Seiner	400	500	25%
Vessel 47	Trawler	425	500	17%
Vessel 48	Trawler	500	500	0%
Vessel 49	Trawler	500	500	0%
Vessel 50	Seiner	300	300	0%

6. Installation and certification process: How does fraud occur?

The procedure for installing and certifying engines involves several steps to ensure that a vessel's engine complies with the limits set out in its fishing licence, without compromising the stability or safety of the vessel. However, there are indications that, in practice, irregularities may occur to circumvent power restrictions, which poses challenges for the control and monitoring of these processes.

Steps to be taken and organisations involved

There are primarily three situations in which an engine may be subject to tampering:

- » during the installation of an engine on a new vessel;
- » when replacing the engine of an existing vessel; or
- » in the context of modernising a vessel.

In any of these three cases, the following procedures must be followed:

1. Application for authorisation from the General Secretariat for Fisheries (SGP).

Before proceeding with the purchase or replacement of the engine, the shipowner must apply for authorisation from the SGP, ensuring that the new engine does not exceed the power permitted in the vessel's fishing licence.

2. Approval by the Directorate General of the Merchant Navy (DGMM). At the same time, the application must be submitted to the DGMM, which verifies that the change does not affect the safety or stability of the vessel.

3. Engine selection and certification by the manufacturer or supplier. Once the above authorisations have been obtained, the shipowner selects an engine that is certified by the manufacturer or supplier, who must issue a technical data sheet with the characteristics of the engine, including its rated power.

4. Certification by a classification society.

Whenever a vessel is classified by a classification society recognised by the Spanish administration (such as Bureau Veritas, DNV, Lloyd's Register, RINA, or China Classification Society), such society will be responsible for inspecting and certifying that the engine complies with the regulations and that its power is in line with the power permitted under the

fishing licence. For unclassified vessels (as in the case of small-scale vessels), this certification is the responsibility of the Harbour Master's Office and the relevant state bodies.

5. Engine installation and power limitation verification. The engine must be installed in an authorised shipyard and under technical supervision. If the fishing licence imposes a power limitation, this must be implemented by the manufacturer or classification society using mechanical or electronic systems that prevent the authorised power from being exceeded.

6. Inspection by the Harbour Master's Office. Once the engine has been installed, the relevant Harbour Master's Office carries out an inspection to verify that the installation complies with seaworthiness and safety conditions.

7. Updating the register and issuing certificates. If the inspection is favourable, the information in the Maritime Register is updated and the corresponding certificates are issued, including the Seaworthiness Certificate and the updated fishing licence.

8. Control and monitoring. The SGP and the DGMM may carry out periodic inspections to verify that the engine continues to comply with the established limits, thus preventing fraudulent modifications that may increase its power.

How does engine power fraud occur?

Fraud may happen at various stages, but especially during the certification and installation of the engine.

» **During the certification stage.** The high number of incorrect certifications and data on engine power that we identified in our study apparently stems from errors or falsifications in documents submitted by fishing vessel operators, engine dealers, or classification societies. Such irregularities often include document falsification, manipulation of performance tests, and the omission of technical requirements. In some cases, engines submitted for certification have specifications that differ from those declared in the official documentation, in order to certify engines that do not comply with the regulations. In most cases, these documents do not accurately or truthfully reflect the engine specifications or maximum power.

» **During engine installation.** This analysis detected cases in which the installed engines do not comply with the declared specifications or in which components have been altered to temporarily increase engine performance and pass initial inspections. Practices have also been documented in which, once certification has been obtained, original parts are replaced with others that increase the actual engine power.

In this way, engines may be tampered with so that they can operate at a higher power than that certified. Article 5.5 of Royal Decree 1044/2022 on Fleet Management introduced a limit of 20% on the 'de-rating' of the engine's maximum power as recognised and certified by the manufacturer. This rule allows, for example,

that if a vessel is restricted to operating with 904 hp, an engine of 1100 horsepower can be installed, and its mechanical or electronic settings adjusted to reduce the maximum power to that stated on the vessel's licence. It is precisely during this power de-rating step of engine installation that many infringements occur. This problem occurs in all types of engines, but it is more common in the most modern and electronic ones, where it is easier to manipulate the settings (the amount of fuel injected into the engine can be altered using various software).¹⁰ To prevent tampering with power settings, countries such as Denmark have banned the de-rating of engine power.

» **During the final inspection stage of the engine installation process.** In this case, fraud can occur primarily because post-installation inspection procedures are inadequate or only partial inspections are carried out, allowing engines that do not comply with current regulations to be approved.

The analysis of these processes highlights the urgent need to strengthen engine power certification mechanisms and improve transparency at every stage of the process. In fact, this is the area where the European Commission is focusing most of its efforts. Following its 2019 study, the European Commission is developing guidelines for Member States to strengthen the engine power certification process, in order to prevent the fraudulent installation and replacement of new engines. However, the solution to the current problem remains unclear, as does what should be done with fraudulent engines that have already been installed.

7. Challenges and solutions for engine regularisation: The horsepower trading market and fishing capacity limits

The findings presented here highlight the need for a massive regularisation of engine power. However, this poses serious structural and economic challenges for the industry, in which the horsepower trading market and maximum fishing capacity limits ('*capacity ceilings*') imposed by the CFP play a crucial role. This is because the CFP sets a maximum limit on the fishing capacity for each Member State, expressed in both tonnage and engine power. Therefore, any increase in engine power on a given vessel must be accompanied by an equivalent reduction on another vessel, which has led to a limited and highly speculative market for the sale and purchase of horsepower among shipowners.

One of the greatest obstacles for an individual shipowner to regularise their situation is the high market price of horsepower. In our case study, each shipowner would need to acquire, on average, an additional 372 hp to regularise their situation, although this number varies greatly depending on the vessel. With an estimated price of 200 euros per horsepower, the total cost per vessel would be around 75 000 euros. This estimated price may in fact be significantly lower than the actual price, as there have been cases in which prices could exceed 500 euros per horsepower, further increasing the economic burden of regularisation.

The high economic costs associated with the regularisation of engines make it essential to launch a state intervention programme to help allocate the horsepower currently not declared in the registers and to legalise existing engines.

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Possible financing solutions include:

- » **Regulation of the horsepower market:** establishing a maximum price for the transfer of horsepower between vessels, to prevent speculative practices and facilitate access to the horsepower required for regularisation.
- » **Interest-free loans:** offering soft loans to buy horsepower. These instruments must be designed including criteria that reduce the risk of generating market inflation and further increasing the price of horsepower.
- » **Amnesty and automatic regularisation:** legalising additional horsepower already installed in engines at no cost to shipowners. Although this would be the quickest and easiest solution to implement, it would create an enormous and unfair disadvantage for those shipowners who have been complying with the regulations for years or have made great financial efforts to regularise their situations.

Beyond the economic challenges, there are two additional obstacles. On the one hand, there is not enough horsepower available on the market to regularise all vessels, and on the other, there is an overall limit on the maximum total horsepower of the Spanish fleet. In fact, according to the CFP (Regulation 1380/2013, Annex II), Spain has a maximum fishing capacity limit of 964 826 kW, which is equivalent to 1 311 796 hp. In 2024, the fishing capacity [declared by Spain](#)¹¹ amounted to 776 332 kW (1 055 516 hp), leaving a legal margin of 256 280 horsepower available for new allocations. Taking into account the size of the Spanish fleet and the volume of undeclared engine power identified in this study, this margin is likely to be insufficient to cover the excess engine power and undeclared fishing capacity.

This means that, in order to regularise the situation of the fleet without exceeding the limits established by EU regulations, it would be necessary to reduce the declared capacity of certain segments of the fleet or to proceed with the selective withdrawal of vessels.

At the same time, this situation highlights the fact that the effective fishing capacity of the Spanish fleet is much higher than that officially registered. This discrepancy generates a significant distortion in the data used for fisheries management, which raises questions about the validity of fishing effort control measures applied on the basis of an evidently underestimated fishing capacity.

In view of this situation, and regardless of the mechanism used to regularise vessels and obtain reliable data on excess fishing capacity, it will be necessary to develop a comprehensive plan to manage the fishing sector.

This plan should include:

- » **A horsepower reallocation mechanism:** designing a transparent mechanism to manage excess fishing capacity and redistribute horsepower fairly.
- » **Incentives for engine replacement:** replacing existing engines with more efficient ones that significantly reduce fishing capacity.
- » **Transition to low-impact fishing methods:** facilitating and incentivising the adoption of more selective fishing gear that is less power- and fuel-intensive, in line with a just transition towards sustainable and climate-responsible fishing. This transition may be accompanied by benefits such as increased access to resources or additional fishing days for vessels that demonstrate a real reduction in their fishing capacity and effort.
- » **Strengthening capacity controls:** implementing effective mechanisms to prevent future irregularities and ensure that fishing capacity remains within the limits established by the CFP, promoting long-term sustainability.

Finally, it is essential to develop a vessel scrapping plan specifically aimed at decommissioning the fishing segments with the highest levels of fraud and where fishing capacity has been identified as being incompatible with resource availability. This approach would allow the fleet to adjust to the reality of marine ecosystems, progressively and permanently eliminating excess capacity and ensuring more sustainable exploitation of resources. To guarantee the effectiveness of this plan, it is essential to establish clear conditions to ensure that capacity withdrawn through vessel scrapping cannot be recovered or reused in the fleet, thus preventing covert increases or fraudulent substitutions of capacity.

It should be emphasised that the problem of engine power underreporting is not unique to Spain. Previous research and the European Commission's audit have highlighted similar irregularities in virtually all Member States. In this regard, any regularisation and capacity adjustment processes at the national level should be accompanied by discussions at the EU level to ensure fairness, avoid competitive distortions among fleets, and strengthen the integrity of the European fisheries control framework.

8. Conclusions

The results of this study reveal the systematic underreporting of engine power and a significant gap between the officially declared fishing capacity and the actual capacity of the Spanish Mediterranean fleet. Ninety-four percent of the vessels analysed have allegedly fraudulent engines, with actual power well above the certified power, while 20% of vessels directly exceed the legal power limits. This massive distortion exposes serious flaws in the engine power verification system and poses a considerable risk to the sustainability of fisheries, the fair distribution of public aid, and the integrity of fisheries management.

Engine power, as argued in Section 3, is a key indicator of actual fishing capacity, especially in trawl fisheries. Experience from the Mediterranean confirms that reducing fishing effort, one of the pillars of the Multiannual Plan for Demersal Stocks

in the Western Mediterranean Sea, will only be effective if accompanied by a rigorous estimate of installed capacity and, therefore, of actual engine power. In this context, the regularisation and verification of engine power are essential conditions for limiting actual fishing capacity.

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Recommendations

Launching a national programme to regularise engine power, with clear objectives, defined deadlines and adequate funding. This programme should consider the following options:

- » Legalising engines that are currently in an irregular situation, in an orderly and transparent manner.
- » Regulating the horsepower market, establishing a maximum price for the transfer of horsepower between vessels, in order to prevent speculative practices and facilitate access to the horsepower required for regularisation.
- » Establishing financing mechanisms, such as interest-free loans, for the acquisition of horsepower on fair terms.
- » Carefully evaluating any measures for amnesty and the automatic regularisation of engine power, avoiding sending signals that would reward non-compliance over those who abide by the rules.

Designing a structural management policy for excess fishing capacity, including:

- » A transparent mechanism to manage excess fishing capacity and redistribute horsepower equitably among the different segments of the fishing fleet, in accordance with social, environmental, and compliance criteria.
- » Engine replacement programmes to reduce effective engine power without compromising vessels' technical viability.
- » A vessel decommissioning plan focused on removing those vessels or segments with the highest levels of fraud or discrepancies between fishing effort and resource availability, accompanied by fair transition measures for affected crews and communities.
- » A plan to facilitate and encourage the adoption of more selective and less power- and fuel-intensive fishing gear, accompanied by benefits such as increased access to resources or additional fishing days for vessels that demonstrate a real reduction in fishing capacity and effort.
- » New tools for monitoring, verifying, and certifying actual fishing capacity, to prevent future irregularities and ensure that fishing capacity remains within the limits set by the CFP.

This report highlights that engine power is an essential variable for the success of any fishing effort control policy, and that engine power manipulation has allowed fishing capacity to remain well above officially recognised levels. In this context, although all debate is legitimate, the current capacity limits established in the CFP should not be relaxed, but rather reinforced. If decisive action is not taken, not only is the sustainability of the Mediterranean Sea at stake, but also the legitimacy of the fisheries governance model as a whole.

References and notes

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- 8 Royal Decrees 1440/1999 and 679/1988, which between 1988 and 2022 regulated fishing with bottom trawl gear in the national fishing grounds of the Mediterranean Sea.
- 9 For the purposes of verifying engine power in accordance with Article 41 of the Fisheries Control Regulation, Member States should establish a sampling plan to identify those fishing vessels or groups of fishing vessels in their fleet for which there is a risk that the propulsion engine power is declared to be lower than the actual power.
- 10 In response to a complaint from individuals about trawlers operating in the Cantabrian Sea (complaint 8091/15/MARE), the Spanish authorities carried out physical inspections of 12 of the vessels reported, without finding any irregularities, which led to the closure of the case. However, four of these trawlers were later inspected as part of the European Commission audit mentioned previously, and it was found that the actual engine power exceeded the certified power in all of the cases inspected. Engine power was between 50% and 200% higher than that certified. How can the enormous difference between the two inspection processes be explained? Although answers may vary, one plausible possibility is that the shipowners had been informed in advance of the inspection and decided to adjust the engine power settings to limit the power.
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